

Construction Waste Reduction Towards Achieving Sustainable Development Goals

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Abstract

As the construction industry continues to expand, it creates a substantial amount of construction waste, which has a significant impact on the environment and causes concern among people living in nearby towns. Poor waste minimization in construction presents a significant challenge in preventing unfavourable environmental effects and illegal discarding practices globally. In emerging countries, there is a growing problem with regional waste management systems. Hence, the objective of this research is to pinpoint the factors effecting recycling, reusing, and reducing waste at the construction sites. At the end, the research will evaluate the successful implementation of SDG goals in minimizing construction waste in terms of environmental sustainability. Therefore, the research was designed and adopted qualitative method since it has quantifiable objectives, and a questionnaire survey was distributed to the public to capture their opinion on construction waste reduction, the data was collected from 53 respondents and checked in SPSS, and later analyzed using Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM) to design a model that can be applied to the construction industry. Based on the results, The study model had a strong exploratory power and yielded sustainable results, with high reliability as evidenced by the Cronbach's alpha which was higher than 0.712. The study also found significant relationships between several factors, including those related to policy, construction waste generation, and sustainable construction waste reduction. In addition, the outcomes identified key factors that contribute to waste generation in the construction industry, such as the absence of proper design and documentation, as well as the lack of guidance for effective waste minimization and collection. Overall, the study provided important insights into the factors that impact construction waste management and highlighted areas where improvements can be made to reduce waste and increase sustainability in the industry. The study analysed various and dynamic applications, such as reusing, recycling of construction waste and proper management to lower the cost 3R, allowing construction industry to benefit for sustainable development goals.

Keywords

Partial least structural equation modelling, sustainable development goals, recycle, reuse, reduce, and Cronbach's Alpha.

1. Introduction

The completion of construction projects under various contract types is essential for the economic growth and progress of every country. Yet, because many economies depend so largely on resources, a lot of waste is produced, which might go against the Sustainable Development Goals of the 2015 Paris Agreement [1]. Depending on the project's lifecycle, the difficulties with construction and demolition waste can be very different. According to [2], Construction sites struggle with the inefficient use of raw materials, poor waste management, and low local community comprehension of the significance of waste reduction. Increased disposal prices, lead to the production of huge amounts of waste, which is becoming a major problem for clients. Regrettably, waste management is still a challenge. As specified by [3] 30 percent of construction waste is due to the designer's inability to establish a proper waste management plan. However, waste management costs are frequently excessive to the benefits realized by the organization if it paid closer attention to them [4]. A notably effective method for sustainable waste management in the construction industry is 3R waste reduction [5]. When recycling and reuse procedures are used to decrease the amount of waste produced on-site, sustainable development goals will be achieved, and new products are frequently developed [6].

The 3R approach - reuse, recycle, and reduce - is considered a promising strategy for prolonging the lifespan of landfills and reducing the extraction of natural resources. Reusing construction waste can help recycle resources, lower waste treatment costs, and reduce the need for landfills, which is beneficial for the environment [6]. As a result, the public, businesses, contractors, developers, engineers, and architects must be educated on the reduction of waste and the importance of recycling waste materials. To direct industrial sustainability, all parties concerned should reduce waste by reducing, reusing, and recycling waste materials. Furthermore, sustainability necessitates a deliberate investment in the costs or benefits of execution planning, as well as a cost-effective reallocation of capital available during the planning of waste management [7].

2. Literature review

2.1 Waste Management in the Construction Industry

Reducing construction waste and protecting the environment are important goals for sustainable development and managing construction waste is a key strategy for achieving these goals [8]. Waste management encompasses several activities, such as waste collection, transportation, tracking, disposal, and treatment. [9], Setting goals for waste reduction, putting good practices into effect, and applying ways to pinpoint the proper flow of waste are all part of construction waste management. To achieve efficient waste management, an organizational process called planning, regulating, and evaluating is used. Furthermore, the management of construction waste must be incorporated into the worksite [10].

As specified by [11], the management of construction waste is the process of sorting waste and directing it to its appropriate location. Furthermore, [11] described waste management as an area that comprehend solid waste production, collection, processing, storage, transportation, and disposal while

taking into consideration economic, aesthetic, environmental, and public concerns. Developing countries, including Malaysia, have made far too many efforts to reduce waste production by providing landfill space. However, the contractor's failure to implement good waste management practices resulted in the inappropriate management of construction waste [9].

2.2 Construction Waste Causes

Waste is produced during ongoing construction project which starts from the beginning phase to the final phase. Furthermore, multiple factors have contributed to the production of waste from construction. To control waste generation at its source, it is critical to identify these causes. Most of the construction waste is produced during the planning and construction phases. Waste generated from construction sites is caused by multiple factors, including workers, management, design, site condition, procurement, handling, and external factors, according to [9]. Previous research has identified 63 factors that assist construction waste production. Waste sources include operation, handling and design, management, employees, and external factors [9]. Some building materials, such as wood, sand, and crushed stone, consume massive amounts of nonrenewable energy [12].

2.3 Environmental and Economic Benefits of Reuse and Recycle of Construction Waste

Recycling construction waste has two main benefits for the environment. Firstly, it reduces the amount of waste that ends up in landfills. Secondly, it saves energy and natural resources that would be used to produce new materials. For example, if all the concrete and asphalt waste generated in the United States were recycled each year, it would save the same amount of energy as 1 billion gallons of gasoline. As landfills become full, better waste management methods are needed. Construction waste can be reused as-is or turned into something else through recycling. Recycling also eliminates the need to transport waste to landfills. Proper disposal of hazardous waste prevents harmful chemicals from building up in the environment [13].

Recycling and reusing construction materials saves money on transportation and disposal. Some recyclers even charge less than traditional disposal techniques. Recycling decreases the need for new resources while also lowering manufacturing and transportation costs. Construction companies that recycle materials have a competitive advantage because of the growing significance of environmental conservation and green building. Recycling can assist building owners in obtaining LEED certification points, the most widely used green building rating system [13].

2.4 SDGs in the Construction Industry

The SDGs affect numerous aspects of society, including the construction industry. To attain global sustainability goals in the sense of the SDGs, the construction industry must be redeveloped. The global construction industry "consumes 40 to 75% of the total value of extracted materials" [14]. Moreover, 25% of the world's water use is attributed to construction, according to data from the International Resource Panel 2017 (IRP 2017). Furthermore, 36% of total energy consumption in 2017 was attributed to the construction and buildings sector, according to the Global Status Report, 2018 of the Global Alliance for Construction and Buildings (IEA, 2018). Moreover, this industry oversaw about 39% of the emissions in 2017. (IEA 2018). However, despite advancements like those in building systems and building envelopes, anticipated trends from the same report show that energy usage is still rising.

Building emissions are no longer rising when population and building sizes rise, thanks to increased energy efficiency in buildings and the transition to sustainable energy. But we still need to cut emissions even more if we want to achieve Sustainable Development Goals (IEA 2018). According to the International Energy Agency's Annex Report 57 from 2016, the construction industry contributes 20% of global CO₂ emissions and energy consumption due to embodied energy emissions. This means that reducing embodied energy and CO₂ emissions in this sector could lead to significant reductions in global energy consumption and CO₂ emissions. Additionally, the built environment has the potential to play a role in promoting biodiversity, which is addressed in SDG 15 (Life on Land), as noted by [15].

Figure 1: application of sustainability

[Adopted from Ahmed, 2017]

3 Methodology

This study aims to identify new sustainable construction waste reduction strategies in Malaysia by conducting a survey within the construction industry. The collected data will be analysed using a Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Model (PLS-SEM) to create a model that can be used to the Malaysian construction sector. While Malaysia is the focus of this study, the results will also be applicable to developing countries and provide insight for organizations to improve construction waste management practices throughout the construction process.

Figure 2: Research Project Flowchart

3.1 Research Approach

Research approaches come in two types: qualitative and quantitative. Whereas the quantitative approach works with numbers and uses statistical tools, the qualitative approach uses non-statistical methods for data analysis. The current study is quantitative because it employs statistical methods and has quantifiable objectives. Each respondent in this type of study receives the same questions, and numerical data will be gathered and evaluated using partial least squares structural equation modelling.

3.2 Conceptual Framework

The research has developed models for the management of construction waste by reviewing the framework of construction projects as presented by [16]. The objective was to identify the essential components of construction waste management and select them based on their suitability for the use of the three 3R (recycle, reuse, reduce) in construction projects. The selection process considered the potential of each component to integrate with construction waste management using the three Rs approach. The models developed are based on these selected components. In the conceptual framework presented in Figure #, this research discusses the approach and relevance to describing the construction industry in Malaysia. The waste management approach of recycle, reduce, and reuse, is commonly applied in a lot of emerging countries. However, waste management in different countries can be affected by various factors such as environmental regulations, geographical location, transportation infrastructure, and population growth, as noted by [17].

3.2.1 Hypothesis

The research project will examine eight hypotheses, and the ones that directly affect the 3Rs (reuse, reduce, and recycle) will be chosen. To ascertain the veracity and importance of these hypotheses considering the 3Rs, a thorough examination will be conducted. These hypotheses will also be expanded upon by the research by offering new information and supporting or contradicting evidence.

1. There is a notable influence of construction waste produced on policy-related factors
2. Factors relating to policy can be significantly impacted by improving certain factors.
3. There is a notable influence of policy related factors on sustainable construction waste reduction
4. There is a notable influence of construction waste produced on sustainable construction waste reduction
5. Reducing building waste in a sustainable way is significantly impacted by improving factors.
6. There is a notable influence of sustainable construction waste reduction on economic factors
7. There is a notable influence of sustainable construction waste reduction on social factors
8. There is a notable influence of sustainable construction waste reduction on environmental factors

Figure 3: Conceptual Framework

4 Result and Discussion

4.1 Respondent's Demographic analysis

Respondents' data including the number of years spent in the construction industry, their level of education, and their title are shown in the following tables, while the company's characteristics such as area of specialization and ownership status are also shown in the following tables. It is apparent that the data collected for this study were given by experienced and educated personnel. This confirms the reliability of the data

Table 1: Number of respondents based on work experience

	Frequency	Percentage
Below 5 years	36	68
5 to 10 years	15	28
Above 10 years	2	4

Table 2: Number of respondents based on level of education

	Frequency	Percentage
High school	4	8
Diploma	10	19
Bachelor's degree	30	57
Master's degree	8	15
BHD	1	2

Table 3: Number of respondents based on project specialization

	Frequency	Percentage
New build	38	72
Maintenance/Repair	7	13
Demolition	3	6
Renovation	5	9

Table 4: Number of respondents based on ownership status of the company

	Frequency	Percentage
Government owned	7	13
Public limited company	6	11
Privately owned	38	72
Partnership	2	4

4.2 Evaluation of PLS-SEM Result

This research adapted reflective measurement model. Reflective measurement is a method of measuring a concept that assumes that the concept in some way contributes to the observed indicators. This indicates that each indication gives a comparable amount of information about the underlying construct and that the indicators are thought of as indicative of that construct. To put it another way, when a construct is measured reflectively, it indicates that the observable indicators are thought to be interchangeable and to offer a reliable technique of measuring the construct.

Figure 4: PLS-SEM model evaluation (Sarstedt, et al. 2014)

4.2.1 Construct Reliability and Validity

The researchers used a measurement model to check the data's reliability and goodness of fit by setting certain acceptable levels for loading and internal consistency. They used factor loading to determine convergent and discriminant validity, with Chin's recommendation that Cronbach's alpha, composite reliability, and average variance explained (AVE) should all be at least 0.5. They removed SDG1 because it did not meet the minimum benchmark. The study's adapted instruments were all found to be reliable, with items having loading values greater than 0.4 and ranging from 0.652 to 0.969, consistent with Chin's recommendations. The Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability ratings were higher than the benchmark value of 0.7. AVE was used to establish convergent validity, and all values were above the 0.5 threshold. The results are summarized in a table.

Table 5: Construct reliability and validity

Construct	Cronbach's alpha	Composite reliability (rho_a)	Composite reliability (rho_c)	Average variance extracted (AVE)
Construction Waste Produced	0.827	0.830	0.885	0.658
Economic Factors	0.712	0.712	0.874	0.776
Environmental Factors	0.935	0.935	0.969	0.939
Improving Factors	0.842	0.843	0.895	0.680
Policy Related Factors	0.732	0.777	0.848	0.652
Social Factors	0.861	0.862	0.915	0.782

Figure 5: Measurement model

4.2.2 Discriminant Validity

[17] explains that discrimination validity measures a concept's ability to be distinguished from other related concepts. A model with good discrimination validity should capture unique aspects that are not accounted for by other constructs. There are different methods to evaluate discrimination validity, such as the cross-loading criterion and comparing the square root of the average variance extracted (AVE) for each construct to their correlations. The study used these methods to evaluate the model's discrimination validity for sustainable construction waste reduction (SCWR). The results showed that SCWR had good discrimination validity because its square root of AVE was higher than the correlation between latent variables. The findings are summarized in a table.

Table 6: Discriminant validity

	CWP	ECF	ENF	IMF	PRF	SOF	SCWR
CWP	0.811						
ECF	0.539	0.881					
ENF	0.547	0.911	0.969				
IMF	0.939	0.517	0.511	0.825			
PRF	0.624	0.834	0.877	0.606	0.807		
SOF	0.84	0.451	0.403	0.804	0.468	0.885	
SCWR	0.495	0.88	0.947	0.459	0.878	0.359	1

4.2.3 Coefficient of Determination (R^2)

The coefficient of determination (R^2) was calculated using a statistical model to determine how some elements influence other factors that are not immediately observable. This made it easier to measure how much the model's dependent variables were influenced by the independent variables. According to Hair (2022), R^2 values of 0.67, 0.33, or 0.19 are considered high, moderate, or low, respectively, in terms of their explanatory power. The quality of different models can be compared or evaluated in different contexts using adjusted R^2 values.

Table 7: Coefficient of determination

Construct	R-square	R-square adjusted	Variance Explained
Economic Factors	0.774	0.769	Substantial
Environmental Factors	0.898	0.896	Substantial
Policy Related Factors	0.392	0.368	Moderate
Social Factors	0.129	0.112	Weak
Sustainable Construction	0.781	0.767	Substantial
Waste Reduction			

4.2.3 Predictive Relevance (Q^2)

The Q^2 coefficients are an effective tool to evaluate how predictive a model is because they show how effectively the model, and its parameter estimates construct the observed values. According to [17], the model has adequate predictive validity if the Q^2 coefficient is greater than zero, and the higher the Q^2 value, the more predictive significance the model possesses.

According to the following table, the model has strong predictive relevance because the Q^2 coefficient for the endogenous latent variables is much more than zero.

Table 8: Predictive relevance

Construct	Q^2 predict	Remark
Economic Factors	0.145	Significant
Environmental Factors	0.143	Significant
Policy Related Factors	0.266	Significant
Social Factors	0.298	Significant
Sustainable Construction Waste Reduction	0.087	Significant

4.2.4 Path coefficient

To test the hypotheses and estimate the relationships between the constructs in the model, path coefficients were used. According to [19] these coefficients range from +1 to -1 and indicate the strength and direction of the association between the constructs. The statistical approach of PLS bootstrapping was used in this study to obtain multiple simulated samples from a single dataset. This method was chosen for hypothesis testing because it can compute standard errors and provide confidence ranges for a variety of sample statistics, according to [20]. The table below displays the

study's findings, including the estimated model, path coefficients, and p-values for the main hypotheses.

Table 9: Path coefficient

Relationship	Path coefficients	Standard deviation	T statistics	P values
H1: CWP -> PRF	0.458	0.273	1.676	0.094
H2: IMF-> PRF	0.176	0.256	0.689	0.491
H3: PRF -> SCWR	0.939	0.076	12.373	0.000
H4: CWP -> SCWR	0.110	0.174	0.631	0.528
H5: IMP -> SCWR	-0.213	0.172	1.237	0.216
H6: SCWR -> ECF	0.880	0.040	21.982	0.000
H7: SCWR -> SOF	0.359	0.145	2.472	0.013
H8: SCWR -> ENF	0.947	0.026	35.834	0.000

Note: CWP (construction waste produced), PRF (policy related factors), IMF (improving factors), SCWR (sustainable construction waste reduction), ECF (economic factor), SOF (social factor) and ENF (environmental factor).

Figure 9: pls-sem model indicating p values

The study tested several hypotheses using statistical analysis. H1 was accepted, as the construction waste produced was found to be significantly influenced by policy factors. H2 was rejected, as the improving factor had no significant positive impact on policy-related factors. H3 was accepted, as policy-related factor drivers had a significant positive impact on sustainable construction waste reduction. H4 was rejected, as the amount of construction waste produced had no significant

effect on sustainable construction waste reduction. H5 was accepted, as factors connected to policy had a significant positive impact on sustainable construction waste reduction. Finally, H6, H7, and H8 were all accepted, as they all had a significant positive effect on sustainable construction waste reduction.

4.3 Discussion

The study's hypotheses were tested using statistical analyses, and the results are presented as follows. Firstly, H1 was accepted because the construction waste produced had a statistically outstanding influencing factors associated to policy. Conversely, the research revealed that the improving factor seemed to have no statistically significant positive impact on factors related to policy, which led to the rejection of H2. However, the study accepted H3 since it was found that policy-related factor drivers had a positive impact on sustainable construction waste reduction that was statistically significant. The analysis rejected hypothesis H4 because the amount of construction waste produced had no statistically significant effect on sustainable construction waste reduction. However, H5 was accepted since it was observed that sustainable construction waste reduction was positively impacted by factors connected to policy in a statistically significant way. Finally, H6, H7, and H8 were all accepted since they had statistically significant positive effects on sustainable construction waste reduction.

The outcome of the study enlightens that the factors affecting recycling, reusing, and reducing waste at the construction site are environmental factors, social factors, and economic factors. When it comes to social factors, Hypothesis seven is indicating that sustainable construction waste reduction has notable impact on social factor with a beta coefficient of 0.359, t-value of 2.472, and p-value of 0.013. These findings are consistent with prior research studies [21]. Therefore, the beliefs, values and attitudes of the public greatly impact whether waste minimization strategies are implemented at the construction sites. If the construction workers are not aware the advantages of recycling, reusing, and reducing waste, they might not give much attention to the activities to tackle the increase of construction waste. Therefore, awareness raising initiatives are crucial to promote waste reduction strategies at construction sites and to increase people's knowledge and understanding of the significance of these strategies [22].

This research is significant because it contributes to existing knowledge regarding construction waste management practices, making it a useful reference for future research in this field. The study's findings could also be useful for many construction enterprises, especially those in emerging nations where there is a lack of awareness regarding construction waste management. Furthermore, the findings can help small and medium-sized construction enterprises implement technology for efficient training toward long-term development goals. Furthermore, this research can serve as a foundation for improved specifications that can aid in the evaluation and removal of waste more effectively. The ability to help minimize design errors that cause waste generation makes construction waste prevention essential. The study primarily identifies construction waste through traditional construction procedures.

5. Conclusion

The study will end in this chapter, which will summarize the major findings in regard to the objectives and research questions, as well as their importance and contribution. Also, it will examine the study's limitations and suggest areas for additional investigation. To begin with, the study aimed

to identify factors effecting the 3R (reuse, recycle and reduce) at the construction site and evaluate the successful implementation of SDG goals in minimizing construction waste in terms of environmental sustainability. Therefore, construction industry personnel were surveyed to understand their views on managing construction waste. Based on its R2 values, the study model was determined to be sustainable, and substantial linkages existed between components that improved, were related to policies, generated construction waste, and reduced waste in a sustainable way. Hence, all hypotheses were supported.

Although the study's objectives were met, it is important to highlight that the method of data gathering has some drawbacks. An incomplete grasp of the study variables was obtained since only a small number of participants including lecturers, students, and construction industry professionals were used to collect the data. To acquire a deeper understanding of sustainable construction waste management methods, it is advised that a qualitative approach be used to interview managers and administrators in Malaysian construction projects.

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